

1 Supplementary Information

2 Should Flexible Mixed Polyolefins be sent to Mechanical or 3 Chemical Recycling: a technology-agnostic analysis based on 4 a Sustainability–Circularity Index.

5 Merel Molenbuur^{1,#}, Cris Garcia-Saravia Ortiz-de-Montellano^{1,2,#}, Steven De Meester^{1,3}, Yvonne van
6 der Meer², Milad Golkaram¹ and Kim Ragaert^{1*}

7 ¹Circular Plastics, Department of Circular Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Science and
8 Engineering, Maastricht University, PO Box 616, 6200 MD Maastricht, the Netherlands

9 ²Faculty of Science and Engineering, Aachen Maastricht Institute for Biobased Materials, Maastricht
10 University, Brightlands Chemelot Campus, Urmonderbaan 22, 6167 RD, Geleen, The Netherlands

11 ³Laboratory for Circular Process Engineering (LCPE), Department of Green Chemistry and
12 Technology, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, Ghent University, Graaf Karel de Goedelaan 5, B-8500
13 Kortrijk, Belgium

14 # equally contributing authors, * corresponding author

15

16 Contents

17	1	Thick-walled products list.....	3
18	2	Mass Flow Analysis (MFA).....	3
19	2.1	Market demand assumptions.....	3
20	2.2	Non-food contact sensitive packaging demand	5
21	2.3	Sensitivity analysis MFA.....	7
22	3	LCA parameters, Impact categories and inventories	8
23	3.1	LCA description.....	8
24	3.1.1	Life cycle inventory (LCI)	10
25	3.1.2	Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA)	10
26	3.2	LCA impact categories.....	10
27	3.3	LCA inventories	11
28	3.3.1	Life cycle inventory data of the unit process for a MR Bench.	11
29	3.3.2	Life cycle inventory data of the unit process for 1 Wooden Bench.	13
30	3.3.3	Life cycle inventory data of the unit process for Cast iron bench.	14
31	3.3.4	Life cycle inventory data of the unit process for Virgin HDPE bench.....	15
32	3.3.5	Jeswani Inventory	16
33	3.4	LCIA - Environmental Impacts of product perspective.....	17
34	3.5	LCIA - Environmental Impacts from a waste perspective	19
35	4	Sensitivity analysis on LCA results	21
36	4.1	Sensitivity analysis on material substitutability.....	22
37	4.2	Sensitivity analysis on lifetime of product.	23
38	5	References	24

39

40

41

42 1 Thick-walled products list

43 In Table S1 below, you can find a list of product examples produced by thick-walled mechanical
44 recycling.

45 *Table S1 Overview of thick-walled product examples (compiled from online search of commercial websites)*

Overview of thick-walled product examples
Palisades
Beams
Fences
Benches
Tables
Planters
Trash bins
Construction panels

46

47 2 Mass Flow Analysis (MFA)

48 2.1 Market demand assumptions

49 The first aim of this research is to understand the availability of flexible mixed polyolefins (fMPO) for
50 thick-walled MR and pyrolysis. To assess this availability, we provide an MFA for each scenario.
51 Market demand assumptions are used and calculated back to the demand of fMPO for each
52 process. These market demand assumptions can be found in Table S2 and Table S3 below.

53 Table S2 provides an overview of the demand assumptions and its sources for thick-walled
54 products from MR of fMPO in 2030.

55 Market demand for MR into thick-walled products was based on the production statistics for a
56 similar product category in the PRODCOM database: 'Builders' ware for the manufacture of
57 flooring, walls, partition walls, ceilings, roofing, etc., guttering and accessories, banisters, fences
58 and the like, fitted shelving for shops, factories, warehouses, storerooms, etc., architectural
59 ornaments such as fluting, vaulting and friezes, of plastics, n.e.c.' (product code [22231990]) in the
60 PRODCOM database [1]. Figure S1 provides an overview for the production rates in the years 2008-
61 2023, with an annual production of 900kt for 2023. This product category does not include several
62 thick-walled products described in Table S1, but likewise some categories included in the category
63 might not necessary be thick-walled products. Therefore, several experts were consulted (three
64 distinct converters of thick-walled products from recycled MPO plastics in the countries of
65 Belgium, the Netherlands and Germany), who estimated a current market demand of thick-walled
66 products of 1 Mt for 2024. Since these numbers are comparable, the estimated 1 Mt is used for

67 extrapolation to 2030 in the demand calculations. This 1 Mt includes all MPO, rigid as well as
 68 flexible (fMPO). A typical 50/50 split across converters is assumed and was confirmed by the
 69 consulted experts.

70
 71 *Figure S1. Production of 'Builders' ware for the manufacture of flooring, walls, partition walls, ceilings, roofing, etc.,*
 72 *guttering and accessories, banisters, fences and the like, fitted shelving for shops, factories, warehouses, storerooms,*
 73 *etc., architectural ornaments such as fluting, vaulting and friezes, of plastics, n.e.c.' (product code [22231990]) over the*
 74 *years, adopted from data from [1].*

75 Based on the expected growth rate as calculated by OECD [2] of 116% for 2024-2030, a total
 76 demand of MPO for thick-walled MR is calculated to be 1,159kt. This total demand includes both
 77 flexible and rigid MPO plastics as input materials. Therefore, by assuming 50% of this demand
 78 coming from flexibles, the demand is 580kt for thick-walled MR from flexibles.

79 *Table S2 S1 Input and output demand assumptions for thick-walled products from MR of fMPO in 2030.*

Description	Number/ percentage	Source/ calculation
Total demand thick-walled products 2024	1 Mt	Expert opinions/ interviews
Growth percentage for plastics from 2024-2030	116%	[2]
Total demand for thick-walled products in 2030	1159 kt	1Mt*116%
Output demand of thick-walled MR from fMPO	580 kt	Assuming 50% coming from flexibles based on expert discussions = 50%*1159kt

80
 81 For CR the focus is on the PP and PE film demand for (flexible) food packaging in Europe in 2030. It
 82 is assumed here that in terms of recycling the source should be similar to the final application, thus
 83 the flexible PE/PP packaging demand should be covered by fMPO packaging waste. Likewise, but
 84 out of scope, it is considered that rigid MPO will be used to satisfy the demand for chemically
 85 recycled PO for rigid packaging (mostly HDPE and PP). Table S3 shows the demand calculation. In

2030, the total PP/PE film demand in 2030 in Europe is estimated to be 15.7Mt [3]. From this total film demand, 23% is used for food packaging applications [3], which equals 3,600kt. The recycled content requirement in Europe, according to the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation [4] for flexible packaging is 10%. This results in a pyrolysis output demand of 360kt from PP/PE film for food packaging ('contact-sensitive packaging') in 2030. Note that the presented MFA only includes projected cracker outputs coming from the purified py-oil of the recycling process. In reality, this py-oil is added alongside virgin naphtha at a typical rate of 12:1-17:1 [5], which allows for the redirection of recycled content credits from the base chemicals proportionally produced by the recycled input to part of the polymers proportionally produced by the virgin inputs (on top of the polymer proportionally made by the recycled input).

Table S3 Demand assumptions for CR from fMPO in 2030.

Description	Number/percentage	Source/ calculation
Total PP/PE film demand in 2030 in Europe	15.7 Mt	[3]
Food packaging demand of total PP/PE film demand	23%	[3]
Demand food packaging	3600 kt	15.7Mt*23% (rounded off to 2 significant numbers)
Recycled content requirement	10%	[4] (for contact sensitive packaging made from plastic materials other than PET, except single use plastic beverage bottles)
Output demand for Pyrolysis	360 kt	3600kt*10%

97

98

99 2.2 Non-food contact sensitive packaging demand

100 While the focus of this study is on the recycled content requirement for food contact sensitive
 101 packaging, the market for non-food packaging films cannot be fully ignored. Therefore, another
 102 scenario was created to understand whether market demand for non-food packaging films could
 103 be met. Here it is assumed that the more pure PE and PP Film fraction is sent to MR where it is
 104 recycled back into film applications. This fraction is of sufficient quality to be used from a technical
 105 point of view [6], but not appropriate for food contact.

106 For the calculations (described in Table S4), the same number of 15.7 Mt is used for the film
 107 demand. By adding the percentages of all non-food bags/ sacks and commercial & industrial films
 108 (excluding refuse bags), the total non-food packaging demand is 57% of 15.7 Mt: 8.95Mt. With the
 109 expected recycled content target from the PPWR on non-food contact sensitive packaging of 35%,
 110 this means that 3130 kt is required to satisfy the demand for non-food packaging. Figure S2 shows
 111 the MR of PE and PP Film in the S0 scenario, as adapted from Lase et al. [7]. It can be seen that the
 112 projected output of MR from pure PE/PP Film is 2050 kt. As the demand for non-food packaging is
 113 calculated to be 3130 kt, there is insufficient material available from the pure PE/PP Film to satisfy
 114 this demand with a gap of 1080 kt.

115 Table S4 Demand assumptions for non-food packaging films

Description	Number/ percentage	Source/ calculation
Total PP/PE film demand in 2030 in Europe	15.70 Mt	[3]
Non-food packaging demand of total PP/PE film demand	57%	All non-food bags/sacks and C&I except refuse bags from [3]
Non-food packaging films in 2030 in Europe	8.95 Mt	57%*15.70Mt
Recycled content required	3130 kt	35% 8.95Mt*35%
Available MR high quality	2050 kt	Based on LDPE and PP flex in S4 scenario from [7]

116

117

118

119 Figure S2 MFA for S0 - Material available for MR based on S4 from [7]

120 As Table S4 shows, there is insufficient material available from the MR of the PE/PP Film bales.
 121 Therefore, it is essential to understand whether chemical recycling of fMPO is able to help meet the
 122 demand for non-food packaging (after the demand for food packaging is satisfied) by adding a new
 123 scenario: S4. Figure S3 provides an MFA of S4, wherein all fMPO input available is processed by CR
 124 (pyrolysis), under the fuel-exempt mass balancing. The total output credited as recycled polymer of
 125 CR in this scenario is 566 kt (156 kt polymer + 410 kt base chemicals). From this 566 kt, 360 kt is
 126 required to satisfy the demand for food packaging (as calculated in Table S3). This means that 206
 127 kt (566 kt – 360 kt) is still available for non-food packaging, which is not enough to close the
 128 calculated gap of 1080 kt.

129

S4

130

131 *Figure S3 MFA for S4 - Scenario in 2030 where all fMPO waste is used as input for CR (pyrolysis) based on the demand of*
 132 *CR for waste-to-polymer + base chemical (fuel exempt mass balancing approach). There is comparatively little PP Flex in*
 133 *the material flow chart, therefore the lines are close to invisible but the text below each flow describes the mass of PP*
 134 *Flex.*

135 2.3 Sensitivity analysis MFA

136 Since this research utilizes process efficiency data from Lase et al. [7] for the MFA, and process
 137 efficiency data from Jeswani et al. [8] for the sustainability and circularity part, it is essential to
 138 understand the influence of process efficiencies on the results. Moreover, changing the material
 139 waste availability also plays a large role in understanding whether there is sufficient fMPO available
 140 to satisfy both the demand of MR and CR. In order to understand the implications of changing
 141 material availability and process efficiencies, a sensitivity analysis was conducted.

142 This sensitivity is based on S3, which means that the fuel-exempt mass-balance approach is used
 143 and thus base chemicals are counted as polymer output. For the sensitivity analysis, the ratio
 144 between polymer output and base chemical output is kept constant (22% polymer output and 57%
 145 base chemical output). The overall CR efficiencies are varied in a range of 50%-90% (in the current
 146 S3 the efficiency is 79%). The input material available in the current S3 is 717 kt, which in the
 147 sensitivity is varied as +/- 25%. Figure S4

148 provides an overview of the resulting amount of available fMPO for MR based on the different
 149 scenarios that are created by changing these two variables. As described in Table S2Table S1
 150 above, the demand of MR is 580kt. As the figure shows, all possible scenarios result in insufficient
 151 material available for MR.

152
153

Figure S4. Sensitivity analysis for MFA: volumes available for MR, based on S3

154

3 LCA parameters, Impact categories and inventories

155

3.1 LCA description

156 The system boundaries include collection, sorting, recycling; manufacturing and assembly of
 157 products; and end-of-life treatment with incineration for fMPO and wood products, and recycling of
 158 steel, HDPE and LDPE, respectively. In the MR pathway, substitution credits were assigned for heat,
 159 electricity, and the proportional amount of virgin HDPE required to produce a bench with equivalent
 160 functional properties (0.55 kg of virgin HDPE per kg of MR pellets in line with previous studies [9]).
 161 Reject streams were modeled as incinerated with energy recovery, with energy credits applied
 162 accordingly. The results for the CR pathway via pyrolysis are taken from Jeswani et al. [8], who applied
 163 a mass balance approach to allocate impacts and credits across the system. Substitution credits
 164 were assigned for naphtha, fossil-based heavy vacuum residue (HVR), char (used as a lignite
 165 substitute), and electricity. Jeswani et al. [8] assumed a yield of 0.9 t of mixed plastic waste (MPW)
 166 entering pyrolysis per t of input plastic waste, in turn producing 0.637 t of pyrolysis oil, 0.07 t of char.
 167 After purification, 0.624 t of purified pyrolysis oil and 0.013 t of HVR are obtained. These outputs were
 168 traced through to LDPE production via steam cracking and polymerization, resulting in 0.5 t of LDPE
 169 per t of plastic waste input. The system boundary was expanded to account for avoided burdens from
 170 secondary material use (e.g., from incineration and RDF), and product yields were credited in line
 171 with a mass allocation.

172 Aligning with Jeswani et al. [8], all systems were modeled for Germany under 2030 baseline
 173 conditions and with End of Life (EoL) efficiencies comparable to existing European plastic waste
 174 management systems [10]. Germany can be considered as a model for (future) European recycling
 175 [11]. Key parameters are summarized in Table S5.

Table S5 Key modelling parameters for the waste and product perspectives

	Seating bench				Food-grade packaging	
	rMPO	FSC-Certified Wood	Cast iron	Virgin HDPE	From CR	From virgin materials (VM)
Functional Unit	Provision of outdoor seating for one person for 30 years using a single bench				Production of 1 kg of LDPE film suitable for food packaging applications (<i>without consideration of specific packaging performance or use-phase</i>)	
Reference Flow	1 bench	3 benches (each 10 years of lifetime)	1 bench	1 bench	1 kg of LDPE output in 4 ratios of CR/VM: 100/0, 50/50, 10/90, 0/100	
System Boundaries	Collection, sorting, shredding, separation, sifting, drying, pelletizing, dyeing, part production, assembly with bolting material, distribution, EoL	Timber production, preservation, part production, assembly with bolting material, distribution, EoL	Cast iron production, transport, casting, assembly with bolting material, weather-resistant coating, distribution, EoL	HDPE granulate production, part production, assembly with bolting material, distribution, EoL	Waste collection and sorting, additional sorting, pyrolysis, purification, cracker, polymerization (a)	Naphtha production, cracker and polymerization (a).
Process efficiency	67% (kg product/kg fMPO input)	N.A.	98% (c)	~100% (d)	62% to pyrolysis oil 50% (t -LDPE/t -fMPO) (a)	~100% (d)
EoL treatment	Incineration	Incineration	Recycling	Recycling	N.A.	N.A.
Substitution Credits	Energy recovery at EoL: Heat (55%), electricity (45%), Lower Heating value 35 GJ/t, 36% efficiency (b) Material recovery credit: 0.55 kg HDPE/kg MR pellet	Energy recovery at EoL: Heat (55%), electricity (45%), Lower Heating value 15 GJ/t, 36% efficiency (b)	Material recovery credit: Cast iron production (98% efficiency)	Material recovery credit: 1 kg/kg, 65% recycling efficiency	Energy recovery from rejects, fossil HVR from purification process, lignite substitute from pyrolysis process, 1 t virgin LDPE/t CR LDPE (a)	N.A.
Geographic Location	Germany for all scenarios					
Temporal Reference	2030 for all scenarios					

Notes:

(a) As reported by (Jeswani et al., 2021)

(b) (de Leeuw et al., 2022)

(c) (Cullen et al., 2012) as mentioned in Table 2 of (Bracquené et al., 2020)

(d) (Hischier, 2007; Kawecki et al., 2018) as mentioned in Table 2 of (Bracquené et al., 2020)

3.1.1 Life cycle inventory (LCI)

For the MR pathway, the LCI was developed using primary data from a dedicated company case study. In contrast, the CR pathway was taken from Jeswani et al. [8] without further modification, to ensure consistency and comparability with the original study. The full LCI datasets of the MR pathway and its conventional material alternatives are provided in section 3.3 of the SI. The LCI for the CR pathway and the associated packaging products is sourced directly from Jeswani et al. [8], see SI, Table S11 for an exact copy.

3.1.2 Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA)

The LCIA was conducted using the ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) method [12], following a hierarchist (H) perspective. Long-term emissions (emissions occurring more than 100 years after the reference year) and infrastructure impacts are excluded from the foreground system. In Table S6 of the SI, the selected impact categories, their abbreviations, and respective units of measurement are provided.

Environmental impacts were modeled using the open-source Brightway2 platform, with Activity Browser as the user interface [13]. To facilitate comparative interpretation, results were further normalized using the Environmental Pricing (EP) method [14], which translates environmental burdens into monetary values expressed in euros per kg of product or functional unit. As mandated by ISO 14044 [15], all individual impact categories are disclosed, while EP normalization is used only as a complementary tool to support the discussion of trade-offs between sustainability and circularity outcomes.

3.2 LCA impact categories

Table S6 LCA impact categories

Pos.	Impact category	Abbreviation	Units
1	Terrestrial Acidification Potential	TAP	kg SO ₂ -eq
2	Global Warming Potential	GWP100	kg CO ₂ eq
3	Freshwater Ecotoxicity Potential	FETP	1,4-DCB eq. emitted to freshwater
4	Marine Ecotoxicity Potential	METP	1,4-DCB eq. emitted to seawater
5	Terrestrial Ecotoxicity Potential	TETP	1,4-DCB eq. emitted to industrial soil
6	Fossil-Fuel Resource Scarcity Potential	FFP	kg oil-eq
7	Freshwater Eutrophication Potential	FEP	kg P-eq. to freshwater
8	Marine Eutrophication Potential	MEP	kg N-eq to marine water
9	Human Carcinogenic Toxicity Potential*	HTPc	1,4-DCB eq. emitted to urban air

10	Human Noncarcinogenic Toxicity Potential*	HTPnc	1,4-DCB eq. emitted to urban air
11	Ionizing Radiation Potential	IRP	kBq Co-60 to air eq
12	Land Occupation Potential	LOP	m ² *a
13	Mineral Resource Scarcity Potential	SOP	kg Cu-eq
14	Stratospheric Ozone Depletion Potential	ODP	kg CFC11-eq
15	Particulate Matter Formation Potential*	PMFP	kg PM2.5-eq
16	Human Damage Ozone Formation Potential	HOFP	kg NOx-eq
17	Ecosystem Damage Ozone Formation Potential	EOFP	kg NOx-eq
18	Water Consumption Potential	WCP	m ³

* Human toxicity and particulate matter formation were excluded from normalization in the waste perspective due to methodological differences in Jeswani et al. [8], which prevent equivalence in impact modeling.

3.3 LCA inventories

3.3.1 Life cycle inventory data of the unit process for a MR Bench.

Table S7 Life cycle inventory data of the unit process for a MR Bench. Reference flow is 1 bench of 84 kg (83kg material + 1kg steel) (1 life cycle)

#	Process	#	Flow	Value	Unit	Selected database
A1	Transport	A1.1	Transport, LKW	16.35	tkm	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, RER
		A2.1	Input quantity	120.93	kg	
A2	Preparation of Pre-sorted fMPO	A2.2	Electricity demand	26.43	kWh	electricity, medium voltage, market for electricity, medium voltage, DE
		A2.3	Output quantity	82.23	kg	
		A3.1	Input quantity	82.23	kg	
A3	Extrusion	A3.2	Electricity demand	37.00	kWh	electricity, medium voltage, market for electricity, medium voltage, DE

	A3.3	Lime	0.82	kg	lime, hydrated, packed, lime production, hydrated, packed, CH
	A3.4	Colorant	3.34	kg	polyethylene, high density, granulate, market for polyethylene, high density, granulate, GLO
	A3.5	Transport of auxiliary materials	1.25	tkm	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, RER
	A3.6	<i>Output quantity</i>	85.57	kg	
	A4.1	<i>Input quantity</i>	85.57	kg	
A4	A4.2	Electricity demand	1.71	kWh	electricity, medium voltage, market for electricity, medium voltage, DE
Assembly	A4.3	Steel profile	1.00	kg	steel, chromium steel 18/8, steel production, electric, chromium steel 18/8, RER
	A4.4	<i>Output quantity</i>	83.00	kg	
	A5.1	Heating oil demand	0.08	kWh	heat, central or small-scale, other than natural gas, heat production, light fuel oil, at boiler 10kW
A5	A5.2	Natural gas demand	15.96	kWh	condensing, non-modulating, Europe without Switzerland
General site consumption	A5.3	Water demand	5.88	kWh	heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, market for heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, CH
	A5.4	Diesel demand	2.52	kWh	tap water, tap water production, conventional treatment, Europe without Switzerland
					diesel, burned in building machine, diesel, burned in building machine, GLO

		A6.1	<i>Input quantity</i>	84.00	kg	
A6	Transport to end customer	A6.2	Transport, LKW	25.20	km	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, RER
		A6.3	<i>Output quantity</i>	84.00	kg	
		A7b.1	<i>Input quantity</i>	84.00	kg	
		A7b.2	Transport to recovery facility	16.80	tkm	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, RER waste plastic, mixture, treatment of waste plastic, mixture, municipal incineration, CH
A7b	End of Life, Option B (incineration w/energy recovery)	A7b.3	Incineration	-84.00	kg	
		A7b.4	Lower Heating Value	9.72	kWh/Kg	
		A7b.5	Electricity recovery (45%) 36%efficiency	-132.30	kWhe/Kg	electricity, medium voltage, market for electricity, medium voltage, DE heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, market for heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, CH
		A7b.6	Heat recovery (55%)	-161.70	kWhh/kg	

3.3.2 Life cycle inventory data of the unit process for 1 Wooden Bench.

Table S8 Life cycle inventory data of the unit process for 1 Wooden Bench. Reference flow is 3 wooden benches of 42.5 kg (1 life cycle)

#	Process	#	Flow	Value	Unit	Selected database
B1	Extraction	B1.1	Glued laminated timber production, MUF-glue – CH	0.09	m ³	glued laminated timber, MUF-glue, glued laminated timber production, MUF-glue, CH

B2	Manufacturing	B2.1	Wood preservation, water-based, no ground contact – RER (preservative treatment)	0.32	kg	wood preservation, oscillating pressure method, organic salt, Cr-free, outdoor use, ground contact, wood preservation, oscillating pressure method, organic salt, Cr-free, outdoor use, ground contact, RER
		B2.2	Steel fasteners: Steel production, electric, chromium steel 18/8 – RER	1.00	kg	steel, chromium steel 18/8, steel production, electric, chromium steel 18/8, RER
B3	Transport to factory	B3.1	Transport, LKW	12.75	km	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, RER
		B4.1	<i>Input quantity</i>	42.50	kg	
B4	Transport to end customer	B4.2	Transport, LKW	12.75	tkm	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, RER
		B4.3	<i>Output quantity</i>	42.50	kg	
		B5.1	<i>Input quantity</i>	42.50	kg	
		B5.2	Transport to disposal, LKW	8.50	tkm	
B5	End of Life	B5.3	Energy recovery	-42.50	kg	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, RER waste wood, untreated, treatment of waste wood, untreated, municipal incineration, CH
		B5.4	Lower Heating Value	4.17	kWh/Kg	
		B5.5	Electricity recovery (45%) 36%efficiency	-28.69	kWhe/Kg	
		B5.6	Heat recovery (55%)	-35.06	kWhh/kg	

3.3.3 Life cycle inventory data of the unit process for Cast iron bench.

Table S9 Life cycle inventory data of the unit process for Cast iron bench. Reference flow is 1 bench (1 life cycle)

#	Process	#	Flow	Value	Unit	Selected database
C1	Bench Manufacturing	C1.1	Cast iron production – RER	95.92	kg	cast iron, cast iron production, RER

		C1.2	Steel production, chromium steel – RER	1.00	kg	steel, chromium steel 18/8, steel production, electric, chromium steel 18/8, RER
		C1.3	Weather-resistant coating	0.20	kg	coating powder, market for coating powder, RER
		C1.4	Electricity, medium voltage – DE	47.50	kWh	electricity, medium voltage, market for electricity, medium voltage, DE
		C1.5	Casting	94.00	kg	casting, steel, lost-wax, market for casting, steel, lost-wax, GLO
C2	Transport to manufacturer					transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, RER
		C2.1	Transport, LKW	28.50	tkm	
		C3.1	<i>Input quantity</i>	95.00	kg	
C3	Transport to customer					transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, RER
		C3.2	Transport, LKW	28.50	tkm	
		C3.3	<i>Output quantity</i>	95.00	kg	
		C4.1	<i>Input quantity</i>	95.00	kg	
C4	End-of-Life					transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, RER
		C4.2	Transport to recycling	19.00	tkm	
		C4.3	Cast iron remelting – RER	95.00	kg	cast iron, cast iron production - remelting, RER
		C4.4	Avoided cast iron (98%efficiency)	-88.45	kg	cast iron, cast iron production, RER

3.3.4 Life cycle inventory data of the unit process for Virgin HDPE bench.

Table S10 Life cycle inventory data of the unit process for Virgin HDPE bench. Reference flow is 1 benches (1 life cycle)

#	Process	#	Flow	Value	Unit	Selected database
		D1.1	HDPE, granulate, virgin – RER	50.00	kg	polyethylene, high density, granulate, market for polyethylene, high density, granulate, GLO
D1	Bench Manufacturing					steel, chromium steel 18/8, steel production, electric, chromium steel 18/8, RER
		D1.2	Steel production, chromium steel – RER	1.00	kg	electricity, medium voltage, market for electricity, medium voltage, DE
		D1.3	Electricity, medium voltage – DE	24.00	kWh	

D2	Transport to manufacturer	D2.1	Transport, LKW	15.00	tkm	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, RER
		D3.1	Input quantity	50.00	kg	
D3	Transport to customer	D3.2	Transport, LKW	9.00	tkm	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, RER
		D3.3	Output quantity	50.00	kg	
		D4.1	Input quantity	50.00	kg	
D4	End of Life, Option A (Recycling)	D4.2	Transport to recycling	6.00	tkm	transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6, RER
		D4.3	Waste plastic incineration – RER	-50.00	kg	
		D4.4	Input quantity	50.00	kg	waste polyethylene terephthalate, for recycling, sorted, market for waste polyethylene terephthalate, for recycling, sorted, Europe without Switzerland polyethylene, high density, granulate, market for polyethylene, high density, granulate, GLO
		D4.5	Sorting	50.00	kg	
		D4.6	Substitution (0.5 q factor + 65% efficiency)	-16.25	kg	

3.3.5 Jeswani Inventory

Table S11 Lifecycle inventory data extracted verbatim from S7 in [8]

Flow	Unit	Pyrolysis (a)	Virgin LDPE
Resources			
Carbon dioxide	kg	2131	122.4
Energy resources			
Crude oil	MJ	4439.1	35311.6
Hard coal	MJ	5622.3	2015.4
Lignite	MJ	2293	2435.1
Natural gas	MJ	30513.1	27938
Uranium natural	MJ	56.6	1732
Emissions			
Inorganic emissions to air			
Ammonia	g	91.6	24.5
Carbon dioxide	kg	-764.5	1609.5

Carbon dioxide (biotic)	kg	2143.4	124.3
Carbon dioxide (land use change)	kg	23	1.5
Carbon monoxide	g	2601.2	947.4
Nitrogen dioxide	g	6	0.6
Nitrogen monoxide	g	109.9	7.5
Nitrogen oxides	g	4428	1806.8
Nitrous oxide (laughing gas)	g	245.5	45.3
Sulphur dioxide	kg	2.3	1.2
Organic emissions to air			
Butane (n-butane)	g	43.8	77
Ethane	kg	0.1	0.3
Formaldehyde (methanol)	g	27.4	5.4
NMVOC (unspecified)	g	262.3	263.6
Pentane (n-pentane)	g	45.8	30.5
Propane	kg	0.1	0.3
Methane	kg	3.8	7.2
Methane (biotic)	kg	2.1	0.1
VOC (unspecified)	g	1106.1	0
Inorganic emissions to fresh water			
Ammonia	g	0.1	0.9
Chloride	kg	17.3	92
Nitrate	g	2151.7	143.2
Nitrogen	g	2.7	0.1
Nitrogen (as total N)	g	3.4	0
Phosphate	g	107.4	7.6
Phosphorus	g	9.6	0.9
Inorganic emissions to sea water			
Chloride	kg	3.3	25.8

(a) Including avoided emissions for incineration of MPW (MSWI (30%) and RDF(70%)).

Note: Data in this table are reproduced verbatim from Table S7 in Jeswani et al. (2021). For more information, please refer to the original source.

3.4 LCIA - Environmental Impacts of product perspective

Results are displayed as a proportional contribution relative to the worst performer, and a table with the numeric results from all impact categories and environmental prices is provided below.

Figure S5. Relative environmental impact by category, using the worst performer (Cast iron) as reference case

Table S12 Environmental impact categories for the lifecycle of four different benches that provide a 30-year seating functionality

Impact categories	Unit	fMPO	Wood	Cast iron	HDPE	Better option
TAP	kg SO ₂ -eq	0.03	0.20	9.93	0.31	fMPO
GWP100	kg CO ₂ eq	179.86	13.71	3432.58	236.91	Wood
FETP	1,4-DCB eq.	0.47	0.50	8.43	0.41	HDPE
METP	1,4-DCB eq.	0.83	1.27	24.80	0.88	fMPO
TETP	1,4-DCB eq.	373.51	1342.50	32020.52	644.67	fMPO
FFP	kg oil-eq	-0.07	5.46	892.45	67.12	fMPO
FEP	kg P-eq.	0.00	0.00	0.16	0.00	fMPO
MEP	kg N-eq	0.00	0.01	0.16	0.00	fMPO
HTPc	1,4-DCB eq.	3.43	8.67	594.40	4.68	fMPO
HTPnc	1,4-DCB eq.	10.89	46.43	1112.41	27.98	fMPO
IRP	kBq Co-60	-0.38	-0.11	21.84	0.41	fMPO
LOP	m ² *a	0.18	166.23	77.21	1.97	fMPO
SOP	kg Cu-eq	0.92	2.74	174.24	2.07	fMPO
ODP	kg CFC11-eq	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	fMPO
PMFP	kg PM _{2.5} -eq	0.03	0.15	7.11	0.13	fMPO

HOFP	kg NOx-eq	0.06	0.28	7.34	0.28	fMPO
EOFP	kg NOx-eq	0.06	0.30	7.60	0.30	fMPO
WCP	m ³	0.07	0.69	18.03	0.91	fMPO
Total Environmental Price	euro	24.02	21.40	582.75	36.07	fMPO

Table S13 Environmental impact categories for the lifecycle of one kilogram of food-grade LDPE at four different compositions, ranging from 100% to 0%

Impact categories	Unit	Percentage of CR material				
		100%	50%	30%	10%	0%
TAP	kg SO ₂ -eq	0.004	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.002
GWP100	kg CO ₂ eq	-0.481	0.702	1.175	1.649	1.886
FETP	1,4-DCB eq.	-0.051	0.261	0.386	0.511	0.574
METP	1,4-DCB eq.	0.004	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.002
TETP	1,4-DCB eq.	-1.103	-0.404	-0.125	0.155	0.295
FFP	kg oil-eq	1.029	1.337	1.460	1.584	1.645
FEP	kg P-eq.	0.005	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.003
MEP	kg N-eq	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001
HTPc	1,4-DCB eq.	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001
HTPnc	1,4-DCB eq.	0.005	0.104	0.144	0.184	0.204
IRP	kBq Co-60	0.001	0.006	0.008	0.010	0.011
LOP	m ² *a	0.847	0.446	0.285	0.124	0.044
SOP	kg Cu-eq	-0.004	-0.001	0.000	0.001	0.002
ODP	kg CFC11-eq	0.003	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001
PMFP	kg PM _{2.5} -eq	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
HOFP	kg NOx-eq	0.005	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.002
EOFP	kg NOx-eq	0.005	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.002
WCP	m ³	0.107	0.058	0.038	0.018	0.008
Total Environmental Price	euro	0.239	0.299	0.323	0.347	0.359

3.5 LCIA - Environmental Impacts from a waste perspective

The environmental impacts of treating one tonne of fMPO waste were evaluated by comparing two recovery pathways: MR of fMPO into pellet feedstock, with energy recovery of the rejects, and CR producing naphtha, fossil HVR, char, and energy substitutes across a range of midpoint impact categories. The functional unit is defined as the treatment of 1 t of fMPO waste. The system boundaries include the collection and sorting of fMPO waste, the recycling processes, and the production of feedstock and substituted products or energy. Even though the ReCiPe method supplies eighteen midpoint categories, only fifteen were considered. Human toxicity (carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic) and particulate matter formation were excluded from the waste perspective analysis to maintain consistency, as the CR baseline [8] uses non-standard calculation methods

for these impact categories. While the results for these categories are reported for completeness, they are not included in the comparative discussion.

Figure S6 displays the difference in environmental impact between MR and CR. Negative values (green bars) indicate categories in which MR has a lower impact than CR, and positive values (red bars) indicate the reverse. MR outperforms CR most significantly in terms of climate change (GWP100), terrestrial ecotoxicity, fossil resource depletion and water use, followed by minor advantages in seven more impact categories. These benefits are largely due to the lower energy demand of MR processes and the substitutability of materials for thick-walled applications (0.4 t HDPE/t fMPO). Conversely, CR shows better performance in freshwater ecotoxicity, and photochemical ozone formation (ecosystems and human health) due to the credits attributed to material and energy substitution from the byproducts (Jeswani et al., 2021). Impact data is provided in Table S14.

Figure S6 Environmental impact differences between MR and CR. Values represent the difference calculated as MR - CR. Negative bars (green) indicate categories where MR results in lower environmental impacts compared to CR, while positive bars (red) indicate categories where CR performs better.

Both recycling routes deliver environmental benefits by diverting fMPO waste from incineration, but the magnitude and nature of these benefits differ. For example, in the climate change category, MR

results in a net reduction of $-189 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{-eq/t}$ of waste, whereas CR still leads to a net impact of $+741 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{-eq/t}$. This reflects the fact that, while CR generates energy and material substitutes, these credits do not fully offset the carbon emissions from pyrolysis. In contrast, MR benefits from lower energy requirements, HDPE substitution, and energy recovery from unrecyclable fractions, contributing to a strongly negative GWP outcome.

When the results are normalized using environmental pricing (see Table S12 in the SI), both recycling routes offer an overall benefit for the treatment of fMPO waste (-91.8 €/t for MR and -361.18 €/t for CR), despite MR achieving lower impacts across most individual categories. The relatively high weighting assigned to ozone formation impacts within the environmental pricing method favours CR. Table S14 below presents the environmental impacts and prices for each pathway.

Table S14 LCIA - Environmental Impacts of waste perspective

Impact Category	Unit	Pyrolysis (CR)	MR Pellets (MR)	Better Option
Acidification (terrestrial)	kg SO ₂ -eq	-1.2	-2.494344726	MR
Climate change (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ -eq	740.8	-189.2208574	MR
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB-eq	-351.8	1.136944976	CR
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB-eq	-0.8	1.555158245	CR
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB-eq	388.4	-262.1192513	MR
Fossil resource depletion	MJ	-621.6	-704.5031932	MR
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P-eq	0.1	-0.00991481	MR
Marine eutrophication	kg N-eq	0.6	-0.002324936	MR
Ionising radiation	kBq Co-60-eq	0.2	-0.981109899	MR
Land use	m ² a	-0.3	-3.305530144	MR
Metal resource depletion	kg Cu-eq	2.2	-4.906025891	MR
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11-eq	0	1.61857E-05	CR
Photochemical ozone (human health)	kg NMVOC-eq	-168.1	-1.908492682	CR
Photochemical ozone (ecosystems)	kg NMVOC-eq	-194.1	-2.066456855	CR
Water use	m ³	55	-8.180937114	MR
Total (environmental prices)	€	-361.18	-91.67963957	CR

4 Sensitivity analysis on LCA results

Given the inherent variability in the technical and processing properties of fMPO [16–18] it is essential to evaluate how assumptions about material substitutability and product use time influence the overall environmental performance of fMPO, therefore two key sources of uncertainty were addressed in a sensitivity analysis: (1) the substitutability of fMPO for virgin HDPE from a waste perspective, and (2) the effective lifetime of a bench from a product perspective.

4.1 Sensitivity analysis on material substitutability

Because CR and MR produce outputs suitable for different applications, direct comparison is not meaningful. Instead, the waste perspective focuses on the value of the outputs relative to substitutable materials. In this case, the basis of comparison is the performance of fMPO in a park bench application to that of virgin HDPE, using tensile strength as a proxy for structural functionality. In practice, the higher strength of virgin HDPE would translate to the bench being made with hollow profiles, rather than the fully dense boards of the fMPO bench.

Due to the heterogeneity of fMPO bales and variability in published tensile strength values, a sensitivity analysis on the HDPE/fMPO ratio (that is, the amount of virgin HDPE required to replace a bench of equivalent performance made from fMPO) was performed. Four scenarios were tested: upper and lower limits based on literature (0.67, 0.71), an average case (0.69), and a “lowest-to-highest” case (0.41), representing the most conservative estimate in favor of HDPE. Our main analysis used a substitution ratio of 0.55, considered a conservative but realistic midpoint. Table S15 below, summarizes the input parameters.

Table S15 Substitution scenarios based on tensile strength values of fMPO and virgin HDPE. Ratios reflect the amount of HDPE needed to match the structural performance of an fMPO bench. A midpoint value of 0.55 was used in the main analysis.

Parameter		Upper limit	Lower limit	Average	Lowest to highest	Unit
Tensile Strength (MPa)	fMPO	23.3 ^(a)	14.2 ^(b)	18.75	-	MPa
	Virgin HDPE	34.6 ^(c)	20 ^(d)	27.3	-	MPa
Strength ratio	(Virgin HDPE / fMPO)	1.48	1.41	1.46	2.44	-
Virgin HDPE required (Kg)	(fMPO mass [84kg]/strength ratio)	56.57	59.64	57.69	34.47	Kg
Substitution HDPE to fMPO (%)	(kg HDPE / kg fMPO)	0.67	0.71	0.69	0.41	%

(a) [19]

(b) [20]

(c) [21]

(d) [22]

Several environmental impact categories showed a high sensitivity to this ratio, most notably ozone depletion potential (+298), terrestrial ecotoxicity (up to +204%), climate change (+177%), marine eutrophication (+127%), and land use (+113%). This suggests that substitutability assumptions require further exploration, especially in bulky applications. The chart below displays the changes in GWP100 at various substitutability ratios.

Figure S7. Sensitivity of the GWP Impact category under the waste perspective, based on varying HDPE/fMPO substitution ratios. Negative values indicate avoided burdens from the treatment of fMPO waste.

4.2 Sensitivity analysis on lifetime of product.

From a product perspective, fMPO benches are modeled with a 30-year lifetime, while wooden benches are assumed to last an average of 10 years, based on industry information. However, real-world replacement cycles are subject to uncertainty, fMPO benches have been proven to withstand over 50 years of use, or conversely, they could potentially be disposed after only 10 years of use, following its wooden counterpart. To account for this, a sensitivity analysis on the impact of varying product lifetimes was performed.

At 10 years of use time, the GWP of an fMPO bench (162.26 kg CO₂-eq) is nearly three times that of a wooden one (56.15 kg CO₂-eq), highlighting the impact of short use cycles. At 10 years of use time, the environmental price of an fMPO bench (€72.07) is more than three times that of a wooden one (€21.40), with a normalized annual impact of 7.21 compared to 2.14. However, extending the service life of the fMPO bench significantly improves its performance: increasing the lifespan from 10 to 30 years reduces the environmental cost per year by nearly 89%, from 7.21 to 0.80. In contrast, when used for longer periods, fMPO outperforms alternatives. A break-even analysis

shows that the fMPO bench must be used for at least 27 years to match the impact of a 10-year wood bench. Virgin HDPE reaches this threshold after approximately 17 years, while steel would require over 270 years of use to break even.

These results (summarized below) underline the importance of aligning material durability with actual service life. Ensuring that long-lasting products like fMPO remain in use is critical to unlocking their circular and environmental potential.

Table S16 Sensitivity analysis on the lifetime of benches

Materials	Scenario	Environmental price	Normalized EP per year of service	Break even relative to the impact of a 10 year wood bench (years)
fMPO	Base case (30 years)	24.02	€ 0.80	
	Low use time (10 years)	72.07	€ 7.21	
	High use time (50 years)	14.41	€ 0.29	26.73
wood	Base case (10 years)	21.40	€ 2.14	
	Low use time (7 years)	30.57	€ 4.37	
	High use time (20 years)	10.70	€ 0.54	10.00
Virgin HDPE	Base case (30 years)	36.07	€ 1.20	
	Low use time (10 years)	108.22	€ 10.82	
	High use time (50 years)	21.64	€ 0.43	17.80
steel	Base case (30 years)	582.75	€ 19.42	
	Low use time (50 years)	349.65	€ 6.99	
	High use time (70 years)	249.75	€ 3.57	~270

5 References

- [1] Eurostat. Prodcom - statistics by product n.d. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/prodcom/database> (accessed July 8, 2025).
- [2] OECD. Global Plastics Outlook. 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1787/aa1edf33-en>.
- [3] Plastics Recyclers Europe & Independent Commodity Intelligence Services [ICIS]. 2023 Flexible films market in Europe 2023.
- [4] EC. PPWR-Final text 2024.
- [5] Kusenbergh M, Eschenbacher A, Djokic MR, Zayoud A, Ragaert K, De Meester S, et al. Opportunities and challenges for the application of post-consumer plastic waste pyrolysis

- oils as steam cracker feedstocks: To decontaminate or not to decontaminate? *Waste Manag* 2022;138:83–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2021.11.009>.
- [6] Bashirgonbadi A, Saputra Lase I, Delva L, Van Geem KM, De Meester S, Ragaert K. Quality evaluation and economic assessment of an improved mechanical recycling process for post-consumer flexible plastics. *Waste Manag* 2022;153:41–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2022.08.018>.
- [7] Lase IS, Tonini D, Caro D, Albizzati PF, Cristóbal J, Kusenber M, et al. How much can chemical recycling contribute to plastic waste recycling in Europe? An assessment using material flow analysis modeling. *Resour Conserv Recycl* 2023;192. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4286637>.
- [8] Jeswani H, Krüger C, Russ M, Horlacher M, Antony F, Hann S, et al. Life cycle environmental impacts of chemical recycling via pyrolysis of mixed plastic waste in comparison with mechanical recycling and energy recovery. *Sci Total Environ* 2021;769:144483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144483>.
- [9] Garcia-Gutierrez P, Amadei AM, Klenert D, Nessi S, Tonini D, Tosches D, et al. Environmental and economic assessment of plastic waste recycling. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.2760/0472>.
- [10] de Leeuw M, Koelemeijer R, de Leeuw AM. Decarbonisation options for the Dutch waste incineration industry 2022.
- [11] European Environment Agency. Municipal waste recycling rates in Europe by country 2024. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/maps-and-charts/municipal-waste-recycled-and-composted-7> (accessed July 10, 2025).
- [12] RIVM. ReCiPe 2016 v1.1 A harmonized life cycle impact assessment method at midpoint and endpoint level Report I: Characterization 2017.
- [13] Steubing B, de Koning D, Haas A, Mutel CL. The activity browser — An open source LCA software building on top of the brightway framework. *Softw Impacts* 2020;3:100012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SIMPA.2019.100012>.
- [14] De Vries J, De Bruyn S, Boerdijk S, Juijn D, Bijleveld M, Van Der Giesen C, et al. Environmental prices handbook 2024: EU27 version methodical justification of key indicators used for the valuation of emissions and the environmental impact. Delft: 2024.
- [15] International Organization for Standardization. ISO 14044: Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines. ISO 2006;2006:652–68. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-011-0297-3>.
- [16] Ragaert K, Delva L, Van Geem K. Mechanical and chemical recycling of solid plastic waste. *Waste Manag* 2017;69:24–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2017.07.044>.
- [17] Golkaram M, Mehta R, Taveau M, Schwarz A, Gankema H, Urbanus JH, et al. Quality model for recycled plastics (QMRP): An indicator for holistic and consistent quality assessment of recycled plastics using product functionality and material properties. *J Clean Prod* 2022;362:132311. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.132311>.
- [18] Roosen M, Mys N, Kusenber M, Billen P, Dumoulin A, Dewulf J, et al. Detailed analysis of the composition of selected plastic packaging waste products and its implications for

- mechanical and thermochemical recycling. *Environ Sci Technol* 2020;54:13282–93.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.0c03371>.
- [19] Blom HP, Teh JW, Rudin A. PP/PE blends. IV. Characterization and compatibilization of blends of postconsumer resin with virgin PP and HDPE. *J Appl Polym Sci* 1998;70:2081–95.
[https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-4628\(19981212\)70:11<2081::AID-APP2>3.0.CO;2-4](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-4628(19981212)70:11<2081::AID-APP2>3.0.CO;2-4).
- [20] Ahmed S, Ali M. Tensile and Flexural Properties of Recycled HDPE for Application in Building Products n.d. <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/202439801038>.
- [21] Kabir II, Sorrell CC, Mada MR, Cholake ST, Bandyopadhyay S. Experimental investigation of mechanical properties of impact modified polyvinyl chloride-fly ash composites. *Society* 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pen>.
- [22] Pattanakul C, Selke S, Lai C, Miltz J. Properties of recycled high density polyethylene from milk bottles. *J Appl Polym Sci* 1991;43:2147–50.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/app.1991.070431122>.

AUTHOR'S PREPRINT